

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR IMPLEMENTING INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS IN THE ACTIVITIES OF PROSECUTION BODIES

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Annotation

This thesis analyzes the theoretical foundations of implementing international standards in the activities of prosecutor's offices. Additionally, the principles of international standards and the issue of their application are thoroughly discussed based on the opinions of legal scholars. Furthermore, the matter of introducing international standards into prosecutorial activities is examined.

Keywords

international standard, prosecutorial activity, supervision, ethics, social security, legal status.

Introduction

International standards of prosecutorial activities serve as an international guideline for implementing prosecutorial functions. International organizations, including the International Association of Prosecutors (IAP), are involved in developing these international standards.

The International Association of Prosecutors, in cooperation with the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, has developed high standards of ethics and professional conduct for prosecutors worldwide based on recommendations adopted in 2014. Specifically, the pillars of these standards are strengthening international cooperation in upholding legality, justice, impartiality, respect for human rights, and combating crime.

The activities of the prosecutor's office have a unique character within the system of state bodies. Important aspects of the prosecutor's office's activities are emphasized, such as the prosecutor's right to act at their own discretion, including decisions on bringing criminal charges or refraining from them, as well as ongoing cooperation with members of society.

The purpose of the IAP is to establish high standards of ethics and professional conduct for prosecutors worldwide, based on strengthening international cooperation in the areas of legality, justice, impartiality, respect for human rights, and combating crime¹.

Modern research indicates a consistent trend towards reassessing the role of prosecutorial oversight in the context of globalization. A systematic analysis of scientific literature reveals the emergence of a new paradigm of prosecutorial oversight that addresses the challenges of the global digital era.

According to **R.Stoykova**, who emphasizes the need to implement innovative control mechanisms, systemic changes in approaches to organizing control activities have been identified. The researcher underscores the importance of developing international cooperation and harmonizing national systems of prosecutorial oversight, noting that traditional forms of oversight are not sufficiently effective in combating transnational crime².

According to **V.A.Mikolenko**, one of the main international legal standards of the activities of prosecutors is compliance with national and international legal documents in their activities. Also, professional and honest performance of their duties, adherence to the principle of the rule of law; prioritizing the protection of human rights. At the

¹ Rekhovsky Alexander Fedorovich. International standards of prosecutorial activities. UDC 343.195.3.

² Ruslan Bilokin. Globalisation and criminal process: Prosecutorial supervision of operational and investigative activities in the context of transnational threats.

same time, when exercising their powers, prosecutors take into account that they act on behalf of and in the interests of society. It consists in striving to maintain a clear balance between the common interests of society and human rights. Implementation of cooperation between the prosecutor's office using the experience of different countries. Raising qualifications and professional level, political neutrality, that is, not being a member of any political party and not openly supporting political parties or participating in campaigning to vote for any political party. Also, the issue of improving the candidate selection process will be carried out based on international standards³.

Within the framework of this study, it is necessary to emphasize one important aspect. The international legal standard of prosecutorial activity is determined by its compliance with the principle of a fair trial enshrined in the European Convention on Human Rights. During the stage of preliminary investigation as well as in the course of direct judicial proceedings, prosecutors are obliged to respect and ensure every individual's right of access to a court and to a fair hearing, and to exercise their powers in an impartial, fair, and independent manner.

Standards governing prosecutorial activity are reflected in normative legal instruments that define the legal status and role of prosecutors, including guidelines on the selection and appointment of prosecutors. These legal instruments provide for a professional-based selection process from among candidates seeking to hold prosecutorial office. Accordingly, individuals aspiring to occupy the position of prosecutor must possess an adequate level of professional competence, high moral integrity, appropriate education and qualifications, and must fully comply with the requirements of professional ethics⁴.

³ Mykolenko, V. A. (2017). European standards of the activity of the prosecutor as a public official. *Constitutional State*, 25, 217-222.

⁴ Order No. 221. General Prosecutor of Ukraine "On the approval of the procedure for passing the attestation by prosecutors". (2019). <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/v0221900-19#Text>

According to **R.V. Mazurik**, another important international legal standard in the exercise of prosecutorial activity lies in the strict adherence by prosecutors to the principles of independence and impartiality when performing their functions. As a result, first and foremost, this standard is aimed at preventing the subordination or dependence of prosecutors on judicial bodies. Each state should establish rules ensuring that the same individual does not simultaneously hold the positions of both judge and prosecutor. Moreover, in the exercise of their powers, prosecutors must not call into question the authority of the courts, must not interfere with the execution of judicial decisions, and must not obstruct an individual's access to the courts for the purpose of protecting violated rights⁵.

According to **A.M.Kulish**, among the international legal standards of prosecutorial activity, particular emphasis should be placed on ensuring state guarantees that enable prosecutors to perform their professional duties under appropriate legal and organizational conditions. The provision of such guarantees should be carried out in close cooperation with prosecutorial authorities. From this perspective, the author considers it appropriate for the state to implement the following forms of incentives and guarantees for prosecutors:

- guaranteeing adequate remuneration, social benefits, and pensions;
- ensuring the protection of prosecutors and their family members;
- ensuring impartial and equal treatment of every employee within the prosecutorial system;
- guaranteeing the right of prosecutors to self-governance⁶.

⁵ Mazurik, R. V. (2021). International standards of prosecutors' activities and their implementation at the level of regional prosecutions. *Current Issues of Jurisprudence. Legal Position*, 1(30), 103-107.

⁶ Kulish, A. M. & Mykolenko, N. S. (2018). Criteria for assessing the effectiveness of the Prosecutor's Office of Ukraine. *Actual Problems of Domestic Jurisprudence*, 2, 85-88.

Standards of Prosecutorial Activity. Significant importance should also be attached to the issue of professional ethics, which serves to define the moral relations governing prosecutors in the exercise of their powers. This contributes to the formation of a favorable environment for collective relations, enhances institutional integrity, and increases the level of public trust among law enforcement personnel, as well as strengthening the authority of the prosecution service and improving its overall effectiveness.

The issue of professional ethics is addressed in a particularly clear and comprehensive manner in the Guidelines on the Role of Prosecutors. In addition to ensuring the effectiveness of protecting citizens from crime and bringing offenders to criminal responsibility, international standards explicitly emphasize the necessity of promoting the application and observance of fundamental principles enshrined in the core human rights instruments.

Conclusion

Taking into account the above-mentioned information as well as the views and opinions of scholars, the following recommendations have been developed regarding the implementation of international legal standards in the activities of prosecutorial bodies. These include defining the legal status of prosecutors in national legislation; improving specialized legislation; enhancing the professional competence of prosecutors; introducing a detailed and transparent selection process for prosecutorial positions; strengthening international cooperation among prosecutorial bodies; and continuing the process of institutional reform.

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